

SHORT COMMUNICATIONS

Chemical Examination of *Flemingia chappar* Ham.—Occurrence of 2' : 4'-dihydroxy-chalcone

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Two crystalline flavonoids and β -sitosterol have been isolated from the powdered whole plant of *Flemingia chappar* Ham. (Fam : Leguminosae). The present report relates to the characterisation of one of these flavonoids as 2' : 4'-dihydroxychalcone, first to be reported from a plant source.

The compound, $C_{15}H_{12}O_3$ (M^+ 240), m.p. 149–50°, crystallising from benzene as yellow needles, gave deep brown colouration with ferric chloride indicating its phenolic nature. The i.r. spectrum disclosed the presence of a chelated carbonyl peak (1640 cm^{-1}), a broad phenolic band (3270 cm^{-1}) and a complex aromatic substitution pattern. The u.v. spectrum (λ_{max}^{EtOH} 260, 320, 340 $m\mu$) was indicative of a chalcone system. The yellow compound was a chalcone as it readily isomerised to the corresponding flavanone in good yield on treatment with 1.5% aqueous sodium hydroxide followed by acidification. The transformation product of the chalcone, $C_{15}H_{12}O_3$ crystallised from benzene as colourless plates, m.p. 189–90° and gave a deep red colour in the Shinoda reaction characteristic of flavanones.

The absence of a methoxyl (Zeisel) and a negative ferric reaction coupled with the ready solubility of the compound, m.p. 189–90°, in aqueous sodium carbonate indicated the presence of a phenolic –OH group *para* to a carbonyl function. The i.r. spectrum disclosed the presence of a strong conjugated carbonyl peak (1660 cm^{-1}), a weak phenolic band (3200 cm^{-1}) and a complex aromatic substitution pattern. The u.v. spectrum λ_{max}^{EtOH} 231 ($\log \epsilon$ 3.70), 277 ($\log \epsilon$ 4.76), 312 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.56) appeared to be similar to that of 7 : 4'-dihydroxyliquiritigenin and the displacement of the 231 $m\mu$ band by 10 $m\mu$ on addition of sodium acetate suggested that the –OH group might be situated at 7-position of the flavanone skeleton¹.

Final confirmation as to the location of the –OH group in the 7-position was secured by synthesis of 7-hydroxyflavanone by the cyclisation of resorcinol with cinnamic acid in the presence of polyphosphoric acid following the method of Hassebe².

The flavanone, m.p. 189–90°, obtained by the isomerisation of the natural chalcone was found to be identical with the synthetic 7-hydroxyflavanone (I) prepared above² in all

1. 'The Chemistry of Flavonoid Compounds', Ed. T. A. Geissman, Pergamon Press, London, 1962. p. 151–53.
2. N. Hassebe, *Nippon Kagaku Zasshi*, 1961, **82**, 1728; *Chem. Abst.*, 1963, **59**, 2761.

respects (m.p., m.m.p., u.v., and superimposable i.r. spectra). This settles the structure of the chalcone as (II).

Studies on the second flavonoid and other constituents are now under way.

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